

LEVEL OF EFFECTIVENESS OF BLENDED LEARNING DURING THE PANDEMIC AND LEARNERS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ARALING PANLIPUNAN

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Level of Effectiveness of Blended Learning During the Pandemic and Learners' Academic Achievement in Araling Panlipunan

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Abstract

This study was conducted to find the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic and learner's academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan at Cabanglasan II District, Division of Bukidnon SY 2022-2023. This study followed the descriptive-correlational research design. It was conducted in Cabanglasan II District, Division of Bukidnon school year 2022-2023. The respondents of the study were all the public-school teachers of the said locale. These are the findings of the study: There was yet a moderate extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment, Attendance, Participation, and Assessment of Learning in Cabanglasan II District. Blended Learning was generally a highly effective blended learning modality during pandemic in terms of Time Management, Comprehension, Independent Learning, Mastery of Competences, and Family Involvement. The learners are quite survivors. They are resilient in the hard test of times and still got high grades despite the changes brought by Blended Learning. The level of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Participation and Assessment of Learning can affect the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan. Comprehension can fairly make a significant relationship to the learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. This study offers the following recommendations: The school heads must intensify their campaign for more support to Blended Learning so that moderate extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment, Attendance, Participation, and Assessment of Learning can be improved. Teachers must perform their roles and functions so that the high effectiveness of blended learning modality during pandemic can be sustained for the welfare of the learners. The learners must continue to uphold their study habits so that they can maintain their grades at its best. The parents must do their share in supporting their children as Participation and Assessment of Learning can affect the academic achievement of their children in Araling Panlipunan. The teachers must introduce more initiatives to hone and develop the comprehension skills of the learners through giving more interactive and interesting reading activities, games, groupings, and home readings.

Keywords: *level, effectiveness, blended learning, pandemic, learner's academic achievement, Araling Panlipunan*

Introduction

Due to the suspension of in-person instruction to stop the spread of COVID-19, the 27 million students in the nation are now enrolled in a "distance learning" system where the primary modes of instruction are online and through modules. As the department contemplates its adoption "following COVID-19," blended learning has been acknowledged as a "good and valid technique" to deliver education.

A learning strategy known as blended learning mixes traditional face-to-face training with internet tutorials. Department Secretary Leonor Briones clarified that the nation has been using distant learning for decades in response to the rising misconception that this is a completely novel strategy. As part of their curricula, many universities have started giving their students access to online courses and assessments. Despite this assertion, there are still difficulties with online learning in the present.

On the other hand, blended learning incorporates in-person instruction along with internet resources and home-study modules. The so-called "blended learning," in which students do not have to attend school every day, may also be recognized as a good or valid method of providing basic education services after COVID-19, according to DepEd Undersecretary for Curriculum and Instruction Diosdado San Antonio.

In order for the teachers to devote greater attention to them when they are in person, he continued, "They can be in fewer classes, with fewer students, and some of their teachings can be learned from home." San Antonio added that piloting face-to-face training "has always been part of the proposals" given by the DepEd during cabinet sessions with President Duterte, saying, "What we propose is truly mixed learning."

It will not be neglected; rather, it will be included in our planning, he assured. President Duterte has earlier rejected suggestions for the pilot introduction of face-to-face classes in response to the COVID-19 delta variant threat. "We'll start with a pilot before establishing face-to-face classes on a big scale." "We really have to concede to the idea that it would be incredibly tough until the so-called 'herd immunity' is developed," San Antonio remarked in reference to the start of face-to-face lessons.

The researcher would like to find the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic and learner's academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan at Cabanglasan II District, Division of Bukidnon

Research Questions

This study was conducted to find the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic and learner's academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan at Cabanglasan II District, Division of Bukidnon SY 2022-2023. Specifically, this aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment, Attendance, Participation, and Assessment of Learning?
2. What is the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Time Management, Comprehension, Independent Learning, Mastery of Competences, and Family Involvement.
3. What is the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the students in Araling Panlipunan?
5. Is there a significant relationship between effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the students in Araling Panlipunan?

Methodology

Research Design

This study followed the descriptive-correlational research design. It investigated the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic and learner's academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan at Cabanglasan II District, Division of Bukidnon.

Data on the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic were obtained through the researcher-made questionnaire and the learners' academic achievement was based on their average grade in the Fourth Quarter of the Araling Panlipunan subject, School Year 2021-2022.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were all the public-school teachers of the Cabanglasan District II, Division of Bukidnon, SY 2022-2023. Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents by school.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents by School

<i>School</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample size</i>
Anlугan Elementary School	10	10
Paradise Elementary School	13	13
San Vicente Elementary School	6	6
Miaray Elementary School	7	7
Tagbacan Elementary School	2	2
Mainaga Elementary School	7	7
Luan-Luan Elementary School	3	3
Kumaliwat Elementary School	3	3
Iba Central Elementary School	29	29
Saluringan Elementary School	4	4
Cananga-an Elementary School	10	10
Manggaod Elementary School	7	7
Sawebseb te Untung teKatablaran	3	3
Total	104	104

Complete Enumeration was used as a sampling procedure of this study. As soon as proper coordination and approval were assured from the Division and District Office, all the public-school teachers in Cabanglasan II District, Division of Bukidnon, SY 2022-2023 were requested to participate as respondents.

Instrument

The researcher was the one who personally crafted the instrument of this study by adapting some portions from the study of Lanojan (2021). It is a survey-questionnaire which was composed of three parts.

Part I was about the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment, Attendance, Participation, and Assessment of Learning.

Part II was on the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of time management, comprehension, independent learning, mastery of competences, and family involvement. Columns for the choices were based on the Five-Point Likert scale. The respondent simply checked the column for his chosen answer.

Part III was about the average grade of the learners in Araling Panlipunan for the first quarter of school year 2022-2023. It was asked

from the teacher handling the Araling Panlipunan subject.

Procedure

This research followed the proper procedure as the institution's standards in conducting a study at Valencia Colleges (Buk.) Incorporated. First, the researcher sought the approval and endorsement letter of the Dean of Graduate School, Dr. Isaias S. Sealza. Then, it was submitted to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bukidnon, Dr. Randolph B. Tortola. When due approval was assured, the researcher approached the District-in-Charge of Cabanglasan II District, Mary-an L. Sumo-oy for her permission. Next, the School Heads of the chosen schools were sought for approval for the researcher to be allowed to conduct a study on their respective schools. Finally, the launching of the questionnaires to the chosen respondents was implemented.

The data were processed and interpreted using the rating scales below. For the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic, the mean was interpreted using the Five-Point Likert Scale.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in this study:

Mean and standard deviation were applied to determine the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic.

Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of implementation of blended learning during pandemic

Percentage and frequency count were used to determine the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan

Pearson r Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r was utilized to find the significant relationship between the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Pearson r Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r was used to find the significant relationship between effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Results and Discussion

This section offers the presentation of findings, the analysis of the problems posed, and interpretation in the light of descriptive research

The extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment, Attendance, Participation, and Assessment of Learning.

Table 2 is the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment.

Table 2. Extent of Implementation of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Enrollment

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teachers were doing home visiting to reach out and enroll pupils who are not yet at school.	4.61	.598	Very High Extent
The government is doing all measures to achieve the target enrollment.	4.53	.696	Very High Extent
Teachers were tasked to conduct barangay mapping to identify and enroll school-age children.	4.42	.733	Very High Extent
Teachers were conducting "Child Finding" to ensure that the school-age children were really at school.	4.39	.716	Very High Extent
Only few pupils have been enrolled as they were afraid of the deadly virus.	2.55	1.386	Low Extent
Overall	4.10	.518	High Extent

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

Table 2 shows that the indicator "Teachers were doing home visiting to reach out and enroll pupils who are not yet at school" (mean = 4.61, sd = .598) got the highest mean. This indicator shows very high extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic. The indicator "Only few pupils have been enrolled as they were afraid of the deadly virus." (mean = 2.55, sd = 1.386) got the lowest mean. It got the lowest mean because in reality, a lot of learners enrolled because of blended learning modality. The COVID-19 epidemic has significantly impacted nations and communities around the globe, upending established institutions in numerous industries and sectors. The sickness has been temporarily contained in the educational sector by closing schools. Nearly 70% of all students worldwide are impacted by these national closures, and millions more children are impacted by local closures enforced in other nations (UNESCO, 2020).

The necessity of education as the cornerstone of all development, despite the crises, cannot be overstated. As a result, the Department of Education works to navigate the changes in order to maintain the delivery of high-quality, easily available, timely, and liberating Philippine basic education services through the implementation of the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). Allowing pupils in basic education to complete their studies is Department policy.

The Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) for the aforementioned Special Curricular Programs (SCPs) are made available by the Department through the Special Curricular Programs Division of the Bureau of Curriculum Development for use by field implementers across the country for SY 2020–2021.

As a whole, the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment was high (mean = 4.10, sd = .518). It reveals high extent of implementation of blended learning because blended learning offers availability flexibility, students like it. In other words, blended learning offers the advantages of face-to-face support and instruction while allowing the student to access the resources at any time and from any location.

Expect to see a stronger emphasis on knowledge application as blended learning tools assist learners in learning through independent discovery and self-paced study. This logical progression will highlight how blended learning provides, promotes, and evaluates experiential learning possibilities for students. Solutions will consequently provide fresh curriculum innovations and even more refined facilitator monitoring tools.

Table 3 shows the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Attendance.

Table 3 reveals that the indicator “Pupils showing symptoms of COVID19 virus are allowed not to go to school” (mean = 4.51, sd = 1.106) got the highest mean. This indicator had very high extent of implementation of blended learning. It means that the implementation was done 9 – 10 times out of ten situations. Other indicators were implemented in moderate extent.

Table 3. *Extent of Implementation of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Attendance*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pupils showing symptoms of COVID19 virus are allowed not to go to school.	4.51	1.106	Very High Extent
The learners only come to school according to their will.	3.18	1.349	Moderate Extent
Attendance in blended learning is not too strict.	3.00	1.329	Moderate Extent
The attendance of the learners was irregular.	2.82	1.335	Moderate Extent
Some parents allow their children to be absent.	2.74	1.220	Moderate Extent
Overall	3.25	.809	Moderate Extent

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

The indicator “Some parents allow their children to be absent.” (mean = 2.74, sd = 1.220) got the lowest mean. The results mean that the implementation of the statements with moderate extent of implementation were done 5 – 6 times out of 10 situations. This means that attendance was not so stable in blended learning since a lot of reasons can make a learner be absent anytime at any rate.

In blended learning is all about in-person training that is combined with some mix of TV/radio-based instruction, online distance learning, and modular distance learning. This represents a teaching strategy that incorporates all types of online distance learning, modular distance learning, TV/radio-based training, or a combination of all three, together with face-to-face instruction. Schools will be able to lessen face-to-face education, encourage social distance, and decrease the number of children outside the home at any given time using blended learning (Llego, 2020).

In overall, the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Attendance was moderate (mean = 3.25, sd = .809). The creation of the necessary teaching and learning resources (LR Portal and DepEd Commons will be utilized to the fullest extent possible), as well as the backing of media organizations like TV and radio stations, will be essential for implementation.

In the era of social media, it has become increasingly challenging to teach students. The days of students listening to a teacher lecture for an hour while remaining submissive and meek are long gone. Blended learning is one strategy we use to re-engage students in the educational process. Using technology, blended learning combines traditional classroom methods with in-class instruction that students can complete at home (Gonzalez, Alfonso).

Table 4 is the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Participation.

As shown in Table 4 the indicators “Learners from families without internet access are not able to participate online tasks” (mean = 4.08, sd = 1.244) and “The parents were showing much efforts to participate in their child’s school programs” (mean = 3.62, sd = 1.064) were in high extent of implementation.

Table 4. *Extent of Implementation of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Participation*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Learners from families without internet access are not able to participate online tasks.	4.08	1.244	High Extent
The parents were showing much efforts to participate in their child’s school programs.	3.62	1.064	High Extent
The learners were showing less participation to school activities.	2.70	1.314	Moderate Extent
Only a few participate in school activities.	2.61	1.257	Moderate Extent
Participation of parents as tutors of their children is not a problem in blended learning.	2.57	1.305	Low Extent
Overall	3.11	.805	Moderate Extent

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

The indicators “The learners were showing less participation to school activities” (mean = 2.70, sd = 1.314) and “Only a few participate in school activities” (mean = 2.61, sd = 1.257) were in moderate extent of implementation of blended learning.

This means that participation is not quite impressive in blended learning. It could be because learners and teachers were still adjusting to this major change. Expect to see a stronger emphasis on knowledge application as blended learning tools assist students in learning

through independent discovery and self-paced study. This logical progression will highlight how blended learning provides, promotes, and evaluates experiential learning possibilities for students. Solutions will consequently provide fresh curriculum innovations and even more refined facilitator monitoring tools.

Generally, there was a moderate Extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Participation (mean = 3.11, $sd = .805$). This modality may not be appropriate for everyone. The ability to be adaptable and vulnerable enough to acknowledge their errors and not take failure personally is a must for educators and administrators. A predetermined pace guide or teacher's manual are not appropriate for reinvigorating student interest in learning. This methodology calls for thorough preparation, introspection, and occasionally on-the-spot revision. Is it necessary for this structure to be adaptable? Every new group of students will have a different set of needs and passions. To be student-centered, culturally sensitive, and suited to student interests, this framework must be adaptive. Our strategy is immediate, intensive, deliberate, and personalized.

Table 5 shows the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Assessment of Learning.

As revealed in Table 5, four indicators were high extent of implementation of blended learning. The indicator "Learning indicators were utilized to validate learners' learning" (mean = 3.98, $sd = .763$) got the highest mean. The indicator "It is difficult to assess learning in Blended Class" (mean = 3.21, $sd = 1.320$) got the lowest mean and it was implemented in moderate extent.

Table 5. *Extent of Implementation of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Assessment of Learning*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Learning indicators were utilized to validate learners' learning.	3.98	.763	High Extent
The learners' scores are difficult to validate in blended learning.	3.80	1.118	High Extent
Assessment in blended learning is just difficult to validate if pupils really got or have retention from it.	3.66	.920	High Extent
Learners' answers are almost impossible to be produced by their age and level.	3.56	.974	High Extent
It is difficult to assess learning in Blended Class.	3.21	1.320	Moderate Extent
Overall	3.64	.670	High Extent

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

It means that its implementation was done 5 – 6 times out of 10 situations. Traditional student-teacher relationships are evolving to become more collaborative and student-driven. Learning that is extremely student-centered, character-building, community-building, and reevaluating resources like time, space, and technology are all key components of personalized learning. Students can now pick where and how to best accomplish their learning objectives by utilizing technology to adapt to new learning methods.

On the whole, the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Assessment of Learning was high (mean = 3.64, $sd = .670$).

The level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Time Management, Comprehension, Independent Learning, Mastery of Competences, and Family Involvement.

Table 6 presents the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Time Management.

Table 6. *Level of Effectiveness of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Time Management*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
The learners were following time management	3.39	.897	Moderately Effective
Learners prioritize their work constantly.	3.16	.893	Moderately Effective
Learners only attend to very important errands in blended learning.	2.94	.879	Moderately Effective
They budget their time to make the most of their blended learning schedules.	2.91	.967	Moderately Effective
Learners are realistic about the time they spend on studying.	2.91	.967	Moderately Effective
Overall	3.07	.732	Moderately Effective

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

Table 6 shows that the indicator "The learners were following time management" (mean = 3.39, $sd = .897$) got the highest mean. It was a moderately effective blended learning. The indicator "Learners are realistic about the time they spend on studying" (mean = 2.91, $sd = .967$) got the lowest mean. The way instructors educate is being redefined, at least in part, by blended learning tools. Therefore, if blended learning develops as an effective educational paradigm, it will challenge the way we select instructors, evaluate their performance, and pay them. A reevaluation of the desirable instructor skills may be necessary as we move away from conventional teaching strategies that are mostly based on the lecture-read-test-repeat model. Expect to hear increased requests for teaching methods that are more dynamic, a fuzziier divide between facilitators' work and leisure time, and a sharper emphasis on pay incentives that are dependent on results.

In general, the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Time Management was moderate (mean = 3.07, $sd = .732$).

Table 7 is the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Comprehension.

Table 7 reveals that the indicator "Blended Learning enhance students' learning outcomes" (mean = 3.34, $sd = 1.085$) got the highest

mean. The indicator “It is effective way for achieving learning objectives” (mean = 3.16, sd = 1.142) got the lowest mean. All indicators in the table show moderately effective blended learning. It means that the effectiveness of these indicators was observed 5 – 6 times out of 10 situations.

Table 7. *Level of Effectiveness of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Comprehension*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Blended Learning enhance students' learning outcomes.	3.34	1.085	Moderately Effective
Blended Learning allows comprehension which is needed to succeed in school, work, and life in general.	3.32	1.082	Moderately Effective
An independent learner in the Blended Learning can comprehend passage and reading materials enabling them to answer on their own.	3.26	1.141	Moderately Effective
Blended Learning improve students' motivation.	3.23	1.054	Moderately Effective
It is effective way for achieving learning objectives	3.16	1.142	Moderately Effective
Overall	3.26	.929	Moderately Effective

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

Student priorities will ultimately determine how blended learning technologies and programs are developed in the market and used for businesses and institutions. Future growth potential will be based on how students engage with one another, share learning experiences, access information, and apply their knowledge in quantifiable ways. The fast-forward of blending learning has already started as tools become more mobile, as students demand more flexible learning options, and as institutions of all sizes respond to changing educational demands.

Generally, the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Comprehension was moderate (mean = 3.26, sd = .929). It was only moderate. It implies that learners were not yet so comfortable with the modality.

Blended learning is most simply defined as the use of both traditional classroom instruction and online instruction to educate the same students the same material in the same course. It is a “well integrated blend of online and classroom learning experiences” (Garrison & Vaughan, 2008). Additionally, there are hybrid programs where students take some classes in conventional classrooms and others totally online.

Table 8 shows the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Independent Learning,

Four statements in Table 8 were highly effective indicators of blended learning. The indicator “Blended learning shifts the teacher's role from knowledge provider to coach and mentor. This shift does not mean that teachers play a passive or less important role in students' education” (mean = 3.73, sd = .927) got the highest mean. This indicator “Blended learning encourages self-learning, where students are forced to look for information online independently, rather than just sitting in a classroom setting and relying on a lecturer” (mean = 3.38, sd= 1.008) got the lowest mean and it was moderately effective indicator of blended learning.

Table 8. *Level of Effectiveness of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Independent Learning*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Blended learning shifts the teacher's role from knowledge provider to coach and mentor. This shift does not mean that teachers play a passive or less important role in students' education.	3.73	.927	Highly Effective
Blended Learning enables fast learners to advance more quickly.	3.66	1.001	Highly Effective
Blended learning enhances the student learning experience by creating opportunities for students to improve their understanding through their own exploration of topics.	3.55	.891	Highly Effective
Blended learning provides greater flexibility of learning for students and enhances student learning experience.	3.49	.955	Highly Effective
Blended learning encourages self-learning, where students are forced to look for information online independently, rather than just sitting in a classroom setting and relying on a lecturer.	3.38	1.008	Moderately Effective
Overall	3.56	.793	Highly Effective

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

Tools and programs for blended learning that make use of social or group learning will keep growing. When students can readily share knowledge, work together on projects, and help one another apply skills, in-class instruction, computer-mediated learning, and facilitator assessments are all improved. To encourage learning between varied groups or based on particular shared characteristics like skill level or interests, look for tools and apps.

Largely, the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Independent Learning was high (mean = 3.56, sd = .793). The method of giving education and learning experiences using a combination of face-to-face and technology-mediated learning is known as blended learning, in other words. During the technology-mediated portions of these learning activities, students are not needed to be physically present together in one location, but they may connect digitally through online communities. For instance, in one blended learning course, students might take a traditional classroom class instructed by a teacher while also autonomously completing online course materials on an online learning platform outside of the classroom.

Blended learning is not necessarily equated with technology integration. It may not be a blended learning system at all, but rather a case of technology integration if online learning is only a tiny component of a classroom-based course and does not give students the flexibility, convenience, and engagement opportunities that online learning affords.

An effective blended learning environment must be created by making the right decisions and overcoming the difficulties that come with technology use. The following issues and suggestions were found in recent research on teacher views undertaken by Athabasca University and the Commonwealth of Learning (Cleveland-Innes, Ostashevski, Mishra, Gauvreau, & Richardson, 2017).

Table 9 shows the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Mastery of Competences.

Table 9. Level of Effectiveness of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Mastery of Competences

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Blended learning allows the use of learning beyond the classroom.	3.84	1.044	Highly Effective
Blended learning allows development of competencies help students draw and build upon what they know, how they think and what they can do.	3.55	.912	Highly Effective
Blended learning develops competencies which are combinations of attitudes, skills and knowledge that students develop and apply for successful learning, living and working.	3.52	.955	Highly Effective
Blended learning allows a competency-based mastery wherein learners can apply what you know—not just learn it, but apply it.	3.52	.985	Highly Effective
Blended Learning can enhance students' learning outcomes, improve students' motivation, and it is effective way for achieving learning objectives.	3.46	.880	Highly Effective
Overall	3.58	.874	Highly Effective

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

All statements in Table 9 were highly effective indicators in blended learning. The indicator “Blended learning allows the use of learning beyond the classroom” (mean = 3.84, sd = 1.044) got the highest mean and the indicator “Blended Learning can enhance students' learning outcomes, improve students' motivation, and it is effective way for achieving learning objectives” (mean = 3.46, sd = .880) got the lowest mean. Thus, blended learning is not totally effective in the elementary level. High school is where blended learning will next see application. Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) are already gaining popularity among high school students and even some advanced middle school pupils. As parents look for ways to get their kids ready for college and compete for top slots at top schools and institutions, the trend is expected to continue growing. This will eventually translate for institutions into students who are ready to go right away, better equipped to interact with the independent nature of blended learning programs and be able to fully benefit from what they have to offer.

Overall, the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Mastery of Competences was high (mean = 3.58, sd = .874). Hybrid or mixed-mode learning are other names for blended learning. The design and execution of these instructional design systems vary across teachers, programs, and schools, and they make use of a variety of teaching and learning experiences. Consider the following examples to obtain a feel of the variety of mixed-mode learning's potential variations: A few teachers at one school use mixed-mode delivery in their separate classrooms. Another situation is an entire program deciding to provide all of its lessons through blended learning, and all of its teachers working together to learn how to do so.

The MELCs for the SCPs were determined based on endurance. If a learning ability lasts with students long after a test or unit of study is over, or if it can be applied to situations outside of a test or unit of study, it is said to be enduring. Examples of such learning qualities that are necessary in various professions and in daily life include research abilities, reading comprehension, writing, map reading, and hypothesis testing (Reeves, 2002; Many & Horrell, 2014).

Keep LCs, merge LCs, rephrase LCs, delete LCs, and/or rephrase LCs were used to create MELCs. If an LC satisfies the endurance criterion, which significantly promotes lifelong learning and is a necessary ability for the following grade level, it is preserved. A single comprehensive learning competency is created when two or more learning competencies (LCs) have the same purpose or learning intention. To be more succinct or, in some situations, responsive and applicable to the new typical learning setup, LCs are redesigned.

Finally, LCs are dropped if they are too specific, have the same articulation as a learning objective, are recurring, already covered by another learning competency, are deemed appropriate to be introduced in an earlier quarter or grade level or moved to a later quarter or grade level, or are any of the following. The performance requirements and policy's content were taken directly from the SCP curriculum guidelines. Its inclusion highlights the fact that identifying MELCs is grounded on established standards and does not deviate from the basic education curriculum. Teachers are therefore urged to dissect the MELCs utilizing the current curriculum guides of the relevant SCP. To help all schools, schools division offices (SDOs), and regional offices (ROs) choose and implement learning delivery strategies that are suitable for the local context and learner diversity while addressing the obstacles given by COVID-19, DepEd offered the MELCs.

Table 10 presents the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Family Involvement.

Table 10 shows that all indicators were observed as highly effective in blended learning in which the statement “Through Blended learning, parent can help their children establish a schedule and take responsibility for their own education” (mean = 3.67, sd = .999) got the highest mean and the indicator “Through Blended learning, parents taught the learners to have higher aspirations, and more

positive attitudes toward school and homework” (mean = 3.53, sd = 1.004) got the lowest mean. The results reveal further that the effectiveness of these indicators was observed 7 – 8 times out of 10 situations. All parents, regardless of their background, want to support their kids and can do it in a variety of ways as long as they can obtain support themselves. In a COVID-affected world, families are in a position to play an even greater role in daily learning by giving teachers crucial context about students' home lives and assisting with instruction. For guardians to be effective, supportive, and confident that they can get assistance when needed, they must feel included.

Table 10. *Level of Effectiveness of Blended Learning during Pandemic in terms of Family Involvement*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Through Blended learning, parent can help their children establish a schedule and take responsibility for their own education.	3.67	.999	Highly Effective
Through Blended learning, the level of involvement is crucial in producing a high impact on the student's performance. The higher the degree of parental involvement, the higher the impact on the child's academic achievement.	3.78	.924	Highly Effective
Through Blended learning, parent and family get to involve and engage to seek input from family members, and to engage parents, guardians and/or family as partners in their children's education and in decision-making	3.66	.910	Highly Effective
Through Blended learning, when parents are involved, students get better grades, score higher on standardized tests, have better attendance records, drop out less often.	3.56	.964	Highly Effective
Through Blended learning, parents taught the learners to have higher aspirations, and more positive attitudes toward school and homework.	3.53	1.004	Highly Effective
Overall	3.64	.854	Highly Effective

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Very High Extent) | 3.40–4.19 (High Extent) | 2.60–3.39 (Moderate Extent) | 1.80–2.59 (Low Extent) | 1.00–1.79 (Very Low Extent)

The pandemic's quick transition to blended learning has been discussed extensively, but the present discourse occasionally forgets that education is a three-way street that includes not just students and educators but also families. When their parents or guardians accompany and encourage them on their educational path and present a united front with their teachers, students of any age do significantly better in traditional school.

Taken as a whole, the level of effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Family Involvement was high (mean = 3.64, sd = .854). Additionally, parents must to be informed and involved. This is a great chance to learn if your main worries are that you don't know how the educational software your child is using works, that you're worried about their safety and privacy online, or that you won't be able to help them with their research the way you used to be able to with offline resources. Families, on the other hand, could be apprehensive or confused about a style of learning that is so unfamiliar to them. This is a normal response because parents are only human and change may be frightening for everyone. Families must therefore help one another if they want to be supportive.

The most popular educational technology (EdTech) tools used in schools are covered in great detail online, and if you don't feel comfortable using a computer, you can always ask your kids' teachers about them or have a conversation with them about them.

The academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 11 is the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 11. *The Academic Achievement of the Learners in Araling Panlipunan*

<i>Grades</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Description</i>
90 and Above	29	27.9	Outstanding
85 – 89	41	39.4	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	33	31.7	Satisfactory
75 – 79	1	1.0	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and Below	0	0	Did not Meet Expectations
Total	104	100	

Table 11 reveals that majority of the learners had grades of 85 – 89 (f = 41 or 39.4%). They had very satisfactory academic achievements in Araling Panlipunan. Others had grades of 90 and above (f = 29 or 27.9%) and 80 – 84 (f = 33 or 31.7%). These learners were outstanding and satisfactory in the subject, respectively. These findings mean that Blended Learning is not negative to learners at all. Their grades can attest to it. The advantages of blended learning for students include better learning abilities, greater informational accessibility, enhanced learning outcomes, and chances to both learn from and teach others.

The following are the main advantages of blended learning, per recent research: Distance collaboration opportunity: As a method of learning, each student works alone virtually on an intellectual project. Increased flexibility: Students may learn whenever and wherever they want thanks to technology-enabled learning, which eliminates time and geographic constraints while still enabling in-person interaction. Increased interaction: Increased interaction between students and between students and professors is made possible through blended learning. Enhanced learning: Different learning activities boost participation and can help students learn at deeper and more worthwhile levels. Students practice intellectual and social self-projection in an online community of inquiry as they learn how to be

virtual citizens. Learning how to utilize a range of devices effectively requires a variety of digital learning abilities, which blended courses help students develop.

The test of significant relationship between the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 12 shows the test of significant relationship between the level of implementation of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 12. *Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Implementation of Blended Learning during Pandemic and the Academic Achievement of the Learners in Araling Panlipunan*

Variable	r	p-value	Interpretation
Enrollment	-.070	.478	Not Significant
Attendance	.082	.408	Not Significant
Participation	.210	.033	Significant
Assessment of Learning	.248	.011	Significant
Overall	.197	.045	Significant

As shown in Table 12 the variables “Enrollment” ($r = -.070$, $p - \text{value} = .478$) and “Attendance” ($r = .082$, $p - \text{value} = .408$) do not have significant relationship with the learners’ academic achievements in Araling Panlipunan. However, the variables “Participation” ($r = .210$, $p - \text{value} = .033$) and “Assessment of Learning” ($r = .248$, $p - \text{value} = .011$) had significant relationship with the learners’ academic Achievements in Araling Panlipunan. The overall test of significant relationship was significant at 0.05 level ($r = .197$, $p - \text{value} = .045$). Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the level of implementation of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

The test of significant relationship between level effectiveness of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 13 presents the test of significant relationship between the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 13. *Test of Significant Relationship between the Extent of Implementation of Blended Learning during Pandemic and the Academic Achievement of the Learners in Araling Panlipunan*

Variable	r	p-value	Interpretation
Time Management	.116	.240	Not Significant
Comprehension	.212	.031	Significant
Independent Learning	.076	.441	Not Significant
Mastery of Competences	.101	.307	Not Significant
Family Involvement	.189	.055	Not Significant
Overall	.164	.096	Not Significant

As revealed in table 13, the variables “Time Management” ($r = .116$, $p - \text{value} = .240$), “Independent Learning” ($r = .076$, $p - \text{value} = .441$), “Mastery of Competences” ($r = .101$, $p - \text{value} = .307$) and “Family Involvement” ($r = .189$, $p - \text{value} = .055$) had no significant relationship with the learners’ academic achievements in Araling Panlipunan. On the other hand, the variable “Comprehension” ($r = .212$, $p - \text{value} = .031$) had significant relationship with the academic achievement of the learners. This means that learners really need to comprehend their lessons so that they can fully adapt to the new learning modality as it sure would affect their academic achievement.

On the whole, there was no significant relationship between the extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic and the academic achievement of the students in Araling Panlipunan ($r = .164$, $p - \text{value} = .096$).

Remember that "blended" is the essential term in blended learning; not all time spent on online tasks should be vilified and seen as taking away from productive study time, and not all learning needs to come from online sources. Student achievement depends heavily on family participation, which is understood as a shared commitment between educators and families to facilitate whole-child development. In typical classroom settings, parent and family interaction has been demonstrated to increase student mastery and social skills, deepen engagement, and lessen behavioral concerns. Engaging with your students' family is maybe more crucial than ever given the shift to virtual learning.

Families have more knowledge than ever about how their children are handling their schoolwork and surviving because student learning is now totally done at home, which brings us to this week's major question.

In order to support student learning and development, educators and parents work together through family involvement. Unlike family involvement, engagement guarantees that families share responsibility for student results and have a voice in their child's education. It goes beyond simply volunteering at school events or sending home one-way messages.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings: There was yet a moderate extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment, Attendance, Participation, and Assessment of Learning in Cabanglasan II District.

Blended Learning was generally highly effective blended learning modality during pandemic in terms of Time Management, Comprehension, Independent Learning, Mastery of Competences, and Family Involvement.

The learners are quite survivors. They are resilient in the hard test of times and still got high grades despite the changes brought by Blended Learning.

The level of implementation of blended learning during pandemic and in terms of Participation and Assessment of Learning can affect the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Comprehension can fairly make a significant relationship to the learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan.

This study offers the following recommendations: The school heads must intensify their campaign for more support to Blended Learning so that moderate extent of implementation of blended learning during pandemic in terms of Enrollment, Attendance, Participation, and Assessment of Learning can be improved.

Teachers must perform their roles and functions so that the high effectiveness of blended learning modality during pandemic can be sustained for the welfare of the learners.

The learners must continue to uphold their study habits so that they can maintain their grades at its best.

The parents must do their share in supporting their children as Participation and Assessment of Learning can affect the academic achievement of their children in Araling Panlipunan.

The teachers must introduce more initiatives to hone and develop the comprehension skills of the learners through giving more interactive and interesting reading activities, games, groupings, and home readings.

References

- Abel V. Alvarez, Jr. Asian Journal of Distance Education Volume 15, Issue 2, 2020. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1285361.pdf>
- Cabanglasan. Retrieved: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cabanglasan>
- COVID-19 Accelerates Blended Learning. Retrieved: <https://www.steelcase.com/research/articles/topics/education/covid-19-accelerates-blended-learning/>
- Get to Know More About Blended Learning in the Philippines. <https://www.ciit.edu.ph/blended-learning-in-the-philippines/#:~:text=Boosts%20Efficiency,virtual%20classrooms%20and%20online%20modules.>
- John Eric Mendoza. (2021). DepEd eyeing blended learning scheme after COVID-19 pandemic. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1450371/depd-eyes-blended-learning-after-covid-19-official#ixzz7Zq3wNORA>
- Larry Ferlazzo — August 19, 2020. Blended Learning in the Age of COVID-19. Retrieved: <https://www.edweek.org/teaching-learning/opinion-blended-learning-in-the-age-of-covid-19/2020/08>

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